

Dietary Vitamin C Supplementation in Farmed Aquatic Animals: A Comprehensive Review

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Abstract:

Vitamin C comprises a group of related water-soluble substances that are crucial to the physiology and health of aquatic animals. Most aquatic animals have a limited capacity to synthesize Vitamin C, thus obtaining Vitamin C predominantly from diets. Because of its ability to scavenge free radicals, act as an antioxidant, and reduce inflammation, vitamin C has become increasingly popular as an ingredient for aquatic feed in recent years. However, the amount of vitamin C that various aquatic organisms require differs substantially from one another. This updated review presents a general outline of the possible physiological function of vitamin C for farmed aquatic

animals, with an emphasis on the information on growth, antioxidant status, immunity, disease prevention, and reproductive performance, as well as the synergistic effects of vitamin C with other micronutrients such as vitamin E, glucans, and metal elements during the past few years. In addition, the interaction between the gut microbiota of aquatic animals and the dietary vitamin C that they consume is something that has been looked into. When it comes to expanding the use of vitamin C in the aquaculture industry, having a solid understanding of the positive functions and mechanisms that vitamin C possesses is of the utmost significance.

Keywords: *Vitamin C, Aquatic animals, Antioxidant, Physiological processes, Synergistic effects.*

Introduction

Vitamins are indispensable micronutrients that are necessary for a range of physiological processes in many species. They have a crucial purpose in preserving the well-being of living

entities, encompassing people, animals, and plants (Peng et al., 2020; Liao et al., 2023; Dawood & Koshio, 2018). Within the realm of nutritional compounds, vitamin C (VC), also known as L-ascorbic acid (AA), comprises a

collection of interconnected substances that are soluble in water. Extensive research has demonstrated the substantial impact of vitamin C on a diverse range of physiological processes, encompassing growth performance, antioxidant status, immune regulation, reproductive performance, and various other metabolic functions (Collins et al., 2021; Ghalibaf et al., 2023; Le et al., 2021; Sarmiento et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022a, b). The association between VC deficit and the pathophysiology of numerous disease processes has been extensively documented in the literature (Plevin and Galletly, 2020; Clijsters et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2016a, b, c). However, it is important to note that the majority of commercially cultivated aquatic organisms, such as fish and crustaceans, possess a restricted ability to internally produce vitamin C (VC) due to the absence of the enzyme L-gulonolactone oxidase. This enzyme is responsible for facilitating the last stage of VC biosynthesis (Grecia et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2022). Therefore, the use of vitamin C (VC) supplements in one's dietary regimen has been suggested as an effective strategy for preventing deficiencies in VC or meeting specific nutritional needs (Le et al., 2021; Sarmiento et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022a, b; Liang et al., 2017; Daniel et al., 2021). Furthermore, the widely recognized vulnerability of VC to degradation caused by thermal heat, and oxidative factors has sparked interest in exploring derivatives that exhibit enhanced stability in laboratory settings, while yet retaining its inherent biological activity in living organisms (Morisaki and Ozaki, 1997). Specifically, amino acid (AA) derivatives containing sulfate and phosphate groups at the labile C2 position within the lactone ring exhibit significant resistance to oxidation and have demonstrated vitamin C (VC) action in aquatic organisms (Lin and Shiau, 2005). Several hydrophilic antioxidants, including L-ascorbyl-2-monophosphate-Mg, L-ascorbyl-2-monophosphate-Ca, L-ascorbyl-2-monophosphate-Na/Mg, and L-ascorbyl-2-polyphosphate, have been identified as having antiscorbutic properties in various aquatic animal species (Dawood and Koshio 2018). Furthermore, it has been documented that L-ascorbyl-2-sulphate exhibits antioxidant activity in several animal species, as indicated by studies conducted by Lee

and Shiau (2002) and Lin and Shiau (2005). In addition, L-ascorbyl-2-glucose is a recently discovered derivative of ascorbic acid (AA) derived from Kimchi. It is an α -glucose conjugate of AA, specifically attached at the C-2 position. This derivative has been found to possess stability against ascorbate oxidase and heat, as reported by Wang et al. in 2003.

Aquaculture, the practice of farming aquatic animals, has emerged as a significant contributor to the worldwide agricultural sector, serving as a crucial protein source for human consumption. This field has experienced rapid growth, as evidenced by the studies conducted by Ogunji et al. (2021) and Verma et al. (2021). In recent years, a significant number of research has been conducted to determine the effects of vitamin C (VC) on the growth, metabolism, health, and other physiological functions of farmed aquatic animals (Le et al., 2021; Sarmiento et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022a, b; Daniel et al., 2021; Özgür, 2019; Mohamed et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2018a, b; Liu et al., 2021; Han et al., 2019a; Villanueva et al., 2022; Kaur et al., 2022; Fazio et al., 2020; Maen et al., 2020; Nasar et al., 2021). The role of VC in aquaculture has been thoroughly examined by Dawood and Koshio (2018), who conducted a comprehensive review and substantial analysis of existing studies on this subject. Since the publication of Dawood and Koshio's seminal study, there has been a substantial body of research, comprising over 160 studies, investigating the impact of vitamin C (VC) on farmed aquatic animals. These investigations have sparked a growing interest in the potential benefits of VC and have stimulated ongoing research into the application of VC in aquaculture (Xiang et al., 2018; Mohamed et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2021; Han et al., 2019a; Villanueva et al., 2022; Kaur et al., 2022; Fazio et al., 2020; Maen et al., 2020; Zou et al., 2020; Hajirezaee et al., 2020; Nasar et al., 2021). Hence, it is necessary to consolidate and analyze the various and fragmented sources of information in a comprehensive assessment.

Consequently, this revised review provides a comprehensive overview of the potential physiological role of vitamin C (VC) in farmed aquatic animals. The focus is on various aspects

including growth, antioxidant capacity, immune response, disease prevention, reproductive performance, and the synergistic interactions of VC with other additives in recent years.

Advantages of vitamin C in Aquaculture

Antioxidant Efficiency

The occurrence of oxidative stress resulting from the attack of reactive oxygen species (ROS) takes place when the antioxidant mechanisms fail to effectively neutralize the harmful effects of ROS, as stated by Zhou et al. (2022). Temperature variation, oxygen availability, and the accumulation of heavy metals and microcystins are significant factors in aquaculture that contribute to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the inhibition of antioxidant enzyme activities. This ultimately leads to oxidative stress and compromised antioxidant defense mechanisms (Yin et al., 2020; Paineofilú et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2019; Birnie-Gauvin et al., 2017). Aquatic organisms have developed a mechanism to mitigate or restore the consequences of oxidative stress, thereby safeguarding themselves from potentially severe damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS). Prevention strategies encompass the utilization of antioxidants, which can be classified as either enzymatic, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx), or non-enzymatic compounds such as vitamin C (VC), vitamin E (VE), and other bioactive molecules (Birnie-Gauvin et al., 2017).

Vitamin C (VC) is a powerful nonenzymatic antioxidant that performs a vital function in the elimination of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which would otherwise interact with nitric oxide (NO) to generate the extremely reactive free radical known as peroxynitrite (Gordon et al., 2020). Additionally, VC serves to safeguard cells against oxidative harm. Vitamin C functions as an antioxidant by transferring electrons to free radicals, thereby counteracting their harmful effects and impeding potential damage (Dawood and Koshio, 2018). Currently, there exists

substantial data supporting the direct involvement of VC in the antioxidative processes of aquatic organisms (Yin et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2016). For instance, the administration of vitamin C (VC) has been found to have the capacity to mitigate the adverse impacts of cadmium (Cd) and lead (Pb) toxicity in Grass Carp kidney (CIK) cells, as demonstrated in studies conducted by Yin et al. (2020) and Liu et al. (2021). Furthermore, similar positive effects have also been observed in Sea Cucumber, as reported by Wang et al. (2016). Furthermore, the incorporation of VC as antioxidants into the diet of *Rhamdia quelen* has the potential to provide supplementary protection against pesticide exposure, including Atrazine (Gomes et al., 2022).

Moreover, a direct association was identified between levels of VC supplementation and the capacities of enzymatic antioxidants, including catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx). These enzymes are crucial components of the biological antioxidant defense system, serving to mitigate oxidative stress (Cai et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2015; Zehra & Khan, 2021). Several studies have reported that the inclusion of vitamin C (VC) in the diets of various fish species, such as juvenile hybrid Grouper and Coral Trout (*Pampus argenteus*), leads to a significant increase in the activity of glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and superoxide dismutase (SOD). Additionally, these studies have observed a significant decrease in the content of malondialdehyde (MDA), which serves as a marker for lipid peroxidation and indicates the extent of oxidative damage (Zhang et al., 2022a, b; Cai et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2022). According to Semra (2023), the use of VC inclusion in in vitro tests resulted in the reversal of alterations in the expressions of *sod1*, *sod2*, *gpx1a*, and *gpx4b* genes. Additionally, the treatment facilitated modifications in the expression of the CAT gene, which had been produced by the administration of copper oxide nanoparticles, in Rainbow Trout gonad cells-2. The Nrf2-Keap1 pathway serves as the primary defensive mechanism against oxidative stress. Under

normal physiological conditions, Nrf2 is sequestered by cytoplasmic Keap1.

However, in the presence of oxidative stress, Nrf2 dissociates from Keap1 and binds to an antioxidant-responsive element. This binding event leads to the activation of transcription for various antioxidant genes, including GPx, SOD, and CAT. These findings have been reported by Bellezza et al. (2018) and Huang et al. (2019), as well as Carmona-Aparicio et al. (2015). Several studies have provided evidence that vitamin C (VC) has the potential to increase the expression of Nrf2 and raise the activities of superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) in order to mitigate the harmful effects of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in aquatic animals (Cai et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2016a, b, c). In addition, vitamin C (VC) possesses the capacity to regenerate additional antioxidants, including vitamin E, hence augmenting the antioxidant efficacy within organisms (Nagaoka et al., 2007; El-Sayed & Izquierdo, 2022). The potential benefits of vitamin C (VC) in mitigating or reversing the impacts of oxidative stress in aquatic organisms can be attributed to its direct antioxidant properties and its ability to enhance the enzymatic antioxidant system (Table 1 - Appendix).

Growth promoters

Aquaculture serves as a dependable means of supplying protein-rich sustenance to effectively address the escalating global food requirements (Simpson, 2011). Over the course of recent decades, the efficacy of vitamin C as a feed supplement has been established in several species of aquatic animals, showcasing its ability to promote growth and maintain physiological homeostasis. For instance, the inclusion of dietary vitamin C at appropriate levels has been shown to have a significant positive impact on various growth parameters in aquatic organisms such as Red Sea Bream (*Pagrus major*) (Dawood et al., 2017; Hossain et al., 2017a, b), Hybrid Grouper (*Epinephelus fuscoguttatus*♀ × *Epinephelus lanceolatus*♂) (Cai et al., 2022), Red Swamp Crayfish (*Procambarus clarkii*) (Kong et al., 2021), Freshwater Prawn (*Macrobrachium malcolmsonii*),

Golden Pompano (*Trachinotus ovatus*) (Zhang et al., 2019), Coho Salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) (Xu et al., 2022), Chinese Mitten Crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*) (Song et al., 2023), Largemouth Bass (*Micropterus salmoides*) (Yusuf et al., 2021), Nile Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Ibrahim et al., 2020), and Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) (Ghafariarsani et al., 2022). Nevertheless, there was a notable disparity in the ideal dosage of vitamin C that was added to the dietary intake of aquatic organisms. The reasons for the considerable variation in requirement values can be attributed to metabolic variations among different species, developmental stages, cultivation conditions, the presence of interacting nutrients in the experimental diets used for evaluation, as well as the duration of the trials (Dawood and Koshio, 2018; Xu et al., 2022). In relation to the regulatory role of vitamin C in the growth performance of aquatic animals, previous studies have suggested that enhanced growth may be attributed to increased feed efficiency in response to dietary supplementation (Ibrahim et al., 2020). Additionally, vitamin C may have a significant impact on nutrition consumption as it is essential for protein metabolism, namely in the synthesis of collagen. Collagen serves as a vital structural framework for cells, tissues, and organs (Yusuf et al., 2021). Prior studies have indicated that vitamin C likely contributes to the carbohydrate metabolism process, facilitating the conversion of glucose into energy in aquatic organisms (Krasnov et al., 1999). Additionally, this vitamin is believed to have an impact on growth performance. The collective impact of vitamin C on the promotion of growth performance can be linked to its ability to boost the metabolic function of aquatic animals.

Furthermore, the consumption of dietary vitamin C has been shown to have a beneficial impact on various aspects of the body, including body composition, digestive enzyme activities, somatic parameters, condition factor (CF), viscerasomatic index (VSI), hepatosomatic index (HSI), spleen somatic index (SSI), and head kidney somatic index (KSI) (Kong et al., 2021; Song et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2021). An experiment conducted by Dawood et al. (2017)

demonstrated that the inclusion of vitamin C in the diet of Red Sea Bream resulted in a considerable increase in body protein and fat content, as well as nitro blue tetrazolium and total serum protein levels. Furthermore, the study conducted by Yusuf et al. (2021) revealed that the inclusion of dietary vitamin C supplementation in Largemouth Bass resulted in an increase in many physiological parameters. These parameters include tissue vitamin C content, whole body crude protein and moisture levels, digestive enzyme activities, as well as the indices of visceral somatic index (VSI), hepatosomatic index (HSI), splenosomatic index (SSI), and kidney somatic index (KSI). In a study conducted by Kong et al. (2021), it was observed that the incorporation of dietary vitamin C had a significant positive impact on both the hepatosomatic index (HSI) and muscle growth rate of Swamp Crayfish. However, Zhang et al. (2019) found no significant impact of dietary vitamin C on the VSI and HSI of juvenile Golden Pompano. The observed variations in outcomes could potentially be attributed to the diverse range of aquatic organisms that were examined, as indicated in Table 1 (Appendix).

Immunostimulant

Vitamin C is recognized in scientific literature as an immunomodulating agent for aquatic animals, as evidenced by studies conducted by Sahoo et al. (2020) and Nme et al. (2020). Vitamin C plays a role in enhancing immune protection by facilitating many cellular processes within the innate and adaptive immune system (Carr and Maggini, 2017). Several studies have shown evidence for the beneficial impact of vitamin C on immunological responses, including enhancements in phagocytic and lysosomal function, respiratory burst and complement activity, as well as serum protein levels (Liang et al., 2017; Daniel et al., 2021; Zehra & Khan, 2021). In a study conducted by Liang et al. (2017), it was shown that juvenile Yellow Catfish (*Pelteobagrus fulvidraco*) exhibited elevated levels of lysozyme, total complement activity, phagocytosis index, and respiratory burst in the head kidney when fed a meal

containing 156.5 mg kg⁻¹ vitamin C. In a study conducted by Daniel et al. (2021), it was observed that the introduction of a stable variant of vitamin C, specifically L-ascorbyl-2-polyphosphate, into the diet of Striped Catfish (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) at a dosage of 350 mg kg⁻¹ led to notable enhancements in respiratory burst activity, phagocytic activity, and serum lysozyme activity. Zehra and Khan (2021) observed a positive correlation between the dietary level of vitamin C and the levels of serum alkaline phosphatase, total serum protein, and lysozyme activities in fingerling *Channa punctatus*. As the vitamin C level in the food increased up to 48.65 mg kg⁻¹, there was a corresponding rising trend in these biomarkers. Furthermore, the impact of innate immunity is not the only factor to consider. Vitamin C may also have an influence on the immunoglobulin M (IgM) levels, which play a crucial role in mediating humoral adaptive immunity in aquatic organisms (Jørgensen et al., 2019). Several studies have shown evidence that the inclusion of vitamin C in the diet of juvenile Hybrid Grouper (*Sillago sihama*) and Grass Carp (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) can lead to increased levels of IgM (Cai et al., 2022; Bellezza et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2016a, b, c). In addition, vitamin C has the potential to promote the differentiation and proliferation of T-cells and B-cells, leading to an increased production of immunoglobulin M (Carr and Maggini, 2017; Kim et al., 2019).

At the molecular level, the consumption of vitamin C in the diet has been observed to influence the expression of genes associated to the immune system in several species of aquatic animals (Zhang et al., 2022a, b; Sahoo et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2018a, b; Dawood et al., 2020). In their studies, Cheng et al. (2018a, b) observed a significant increase in the expression levels of genes associated with pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as *tnf-α* and *il-6*, in the liver of juvenile Puffer fish (*Takifugu obscurus*) when supplemented with dietary vitamin C. Previous studies have demonstrated that the inclusion of

an optimal concentration of Vitamin C in the diet of Blunt Snout Bream, Nile Tilapia, and *Rhynchocypris lagowskii* can result in an up-regulation of *tnf-α* and *il-1* expression in the serum, intestine, and spleen of aquatic animals (Dawood et al., 2020; Wang, 2019; Zhu et al., 2023). This effect may be attributed to the ability of vitamin C to enhance the differentiation of immune response into Th1 cells, subsequently promoting the production of TNF- α and IL-1 (Wang, 2019; Zhu et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2012). Sahoo et al. (2020) reported an elevated gene expression pattern of Type-I interferons (I-IFNs) in *Labeo bata* specimens that were administered a diet containing 200 mg kg⁻¹ vitamin C. This upregulation of I-IFNs was found to confer a protective effect against infection. Furthermore, a study conducted using in vitro experimentation revealed a noteworthy increase in the relative mRNA expression of immune-related genes, such as prophenoloxidase, serine proteases, α -2 microglobulin, and anti-lipopolysaccharide factor-1, in the hemocytes of Swimming Crabs (*Portunus trituberculatus*) when supplemented with vitamin C media (Perveen et al., 2021). Collectively, vitamin C has a significant function in regulating the immune defense system and enhancing the defense mechanisms of aquatic animals against infections (Table 1 - Appendix).

Enhancement of Reproductive Performance

The study conducted by DiTroia et al. (2019) indicates that a shortage in maternal vitamin C has a negative impact on the reproductive health of adult offspring. Specifically, it results in a decrease in the quantity of germ cells, a delay in the process of meiosis, and a reduction in fecundity. The involvement of vitamin C is of utmost importance in the biosynthesis of norepinephrine and epinephrine in aquatic organisms. Norepinephrine exerts direct stimulatory effects on the release of hypothalamic gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), a factor closely associated with the reproductive development of animals (NRC 2011; Francisco et al. 2002). As an illustration,

Betsy et al. (2021) observed an elevation in the gonadosomatic index (GSI) of Koi Carp (*Cyprinus carpio* L.) following the administration of feed enriched with 600 mg kg⁻¹ of vitamin C. Martins et al. (2016), Shahkar et al. (2015), and Castro et al. (2019) have reported a comparable promotional impact of VC in Nile Tilapia, Japanese Eel (*Anguilla japonica*), and Lebranche Mullet (*Mugil liza*). In contrast, the study conducted by Shao et al. (2018) shown that the consumption of dietary vitamin C at a concentration of 444.1 mg kg⁻¹ resulted in a significant postponement of ovary development in on-growing Gibel Carp (*Carassius auratus gibelio*), as evidenced by changes in gonadosomatic index (GSI), gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) levels, and ovarian stages. These inconsistencies may be attributed to variations in the species under investigation, as well as differences in developmental stages.

In recent years, numerous studies have demonstrated that vitamin C possesses the ability to autonomously stimulate diverse cellular pathways involved in the regulation of cell cycle, resulting in enhanced cell division and proliferation across different species (Liso et al., 1984; Heidari-Zefreh et al., 2019; Hajime et al., 2012; Francis et al., 2012). The gonad histological analysis revealed a notable rise in spermatogonia count in Japanese eel and Nile Tilapia when dietary vitamin C was increased. This observed effect may be attributed to the protective role of vitamin C in safeguarding germ cells against DNA damage and the oxidation of seminal plasma proteins caused by reactive oxygen radicals. Additionally, vitamin C is known to influence collagen production by regulating prolyl hydroxylation, as highlighted in studies conducted by Shahkar et al. (2015) and Perera and Bhujel (2021). Furthermore, Castro et al. (2019) reported that the addition of vitamin C to the diet has the potential to enhance the quality of sperm in Lebranche Mullet (*Mugil liza*). This improvement is observed in various aspects such as motility time, motility rate, spermatid density, and cell membrane integrity. The underlying mechanism for this enhancement can be attributed to the protective properties of vitamin C, which help in reducing oxidative

stress. In addition, the administration of vitamin C inclusion has been found to enhance fertility and extend the duration of egg maturation in Starry Flounder (*Platichthys stellatus*) (Wang et al., 2014). The positive impacts of vitamin C on the reproductive performance of aquatic animals are commonly ascribed to its facilitation of hormone release and mitigation of oxidative stress.

Diseases Inhibitors

In the field of aquaculture, it has been observed that Vitamin C has a beneficial impact on the prevention and management of diseases caused by pathogen infections, as documented by Le et al. (2021) and Han et al. (2020). As demonstrated by Le et al. (2021), the inclusion of vitamin C supplement in the dietary regimen of *Psammoderus waigiensis*, commonly known as Waigieu Seaperch, resulted in elevated levels of white blood cells and higher activity of plasma lysozyme. Consequently, the mortality rate of these fish decreased when they were exposed to *Streptococcus iniae*. The dietary supplementation of vitamin C demonstrated a notable enhancement in the survival rate of Coral Trout when exposed to *Vibrio harveyi*, Striped Catfish when challenged with *Aeromonas hydrophila*, and Nile Tilapia when challenged with *S. agalactiae* or *Aeromonas sobria*. This improvement can be attributed to the potent antioxidant properties and immune-stimulating capabilities of vitamin C, as reported in studies conducted by Daniel et al. (2021), El Basuini et al. (2021), Ibrahim et al. (2020), and Zhu et al. (2022). Furthermore, the incorporation of dietary vitamin C demonstrated a rise in the quantity of haemocytes and preservation of the structural integrity of haemocytes in *Cherax quadricarinatus*. This dietary supplementation also shown an enhanced immunoprotective effect against infection caused by the White Spot Syndrome Virus (Zuo et al., 2022). In addition to its use as a feed additive, the introduction of a substantial quantity of sodium ascorbate (L-ascorbic acid sodium) into the marine environment (specifically sea water) was found to confer protection to Brine Shrimp larvae (*Artemia franciscana*) against infection caused by *V. harveyi*. This protective effect was observed to coincide with the activation of heat shock

protein 70 (Han et al., 2019b). The primary mechanism via which vitamin C enhances the resistance of aquatic animals to pathogen attack is predominantly attributed to its antioxidant and immune-stimulating properties.

Regulation of the intestinal microbiota

The presence of intestinal bacteria plays a vital role in maintaining the nutritional and overall well-being of the host. However, in various disorders, there is often an imbalance in the composition of these microbial communities (Diwan et al., 2022; Fei et al., 2022). The existing body of research suggests that the manipulation of nutritional factors can have a positive impact on the composition and function of gut microbiota, hence offering potential therapeutic benefits (Vargas-Albores et al., 2021). Multiple studies have provided evidence that the supplementation of vitamin C has effects on the modulation of microbiota in persons who are in good health, resulting in various advantageous alterations in bacterial populations (Otten et al., 2021; Dong et al., 2020). Previous research has demonstrated that the presence of *Lactobacillus* and *Bacillus* in the digestive tract of aquatic animals increased, but the abundance of *Escherichia coli* dropped, as the dietary levels of vitamin C increased up to 45.1 mg kg⁻¹ in juvenile Jian Carp (*Cyprinus carpio* var. Jian) (Liu et al., 2011). In a recent study conducted by Zeng et al. (2021), it was observed that the inclusion of dietary VC at a concentration of 5000 mg kg⁻¹ resulted in a considerable increase in the abundance of *Haloferula* in Sea Cucumber. According to a study conducted by Eduardo et al. (2022), the introduction of a diet containing 2 g kg⁻¹ to Pacific White Shrimp (*Penaeus vannamei*) infected with acute hepatopancreatic necrosis diseases led to a decrease in Alphaproteobacteria and an increase in Alteromonadales. In general, there exists a body of studies indicating that the inclusion of vitamin C in the diet may have an impact on the intestinal microbiota of aquatic animals. However, while these findings are intriguing in terms of their potential to enhance nutritional and health outcomes, they have not yet been thoroughly explored and therefore warrant additional exploration.

The Potential Synergistic Effects of Vitamin C and Other Supplements on Aquatic Animals

Vitamin C and glucans

The immunomodulatory effects of β -glucan have been well-documented, with its unique physicochemical characteristics playing a crucial role in determining the extent of its binding to macrophage receptors and subsequent modulation of immunological responses (Wu et al., 2023). The investigation of the interaction between β -glucans and Vitamin C in aquatic animals has been a subject of research for several decades. In previous studies conducted by Barros et al. (2015), Dawood et al. (2017), Wu et al. (2020), and Wu et al. (2016), it was observed that Nile Tilapia, Red Seabream, Tiger Grouper, and White Shrimp exhibited augmented innate immune responses when supplemented with β -glucans and Vitamin C. According to Wu et al. (2020), the incorporation of β -glucans and Vitamin C in the diet of Tiger Grouper has been found to enhance their tolerance to transportation stress in some species. An interaction between β -1,3-glucan paramylon (PML) and Vitamin C was found to have a synergistic effect on acid phosphatase activity in the anterior section of the intestine, as well as on the respiratory burst of whole-blood in Hybrid Striped Bass (*Morone chrysops* $\times$ *M. saxatilis*). The interaction between these two additions was primarily assessed in vitro with regards to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and a modest improvement in immune responses was observed in vivo during the feeding study conducted by Yamamoto et al. (2020) (Table 2 - Appendix).

Vitamin C and vitamin E

According to El-Sayed and Izquierdo (2022), Vitamin E serves as a structural constituent of cellular membranes and possesses a robust chain-breaking antioxidant mechanism. This characteristic renders Vitamin E crucial in numerous biological processes. In recent years, a number of studies have demonstrated the capacity of vitamin E to stimulate growth performance and antioxidation (Wu et al., 2017;

Li et al., 2018), enhance immune response (Saheli et al., 2021), and improve reproductive efficiency and flesh quality in aquatic animals (Me and Ta, 2019; Zhang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022a, b). The capacity of vitamin C to regenerate or protect vitamin E from membrane α -tocopherol radicals is essential for its antioxidative role (Jiménez-Fernández et al., 2015). On recent times, considerable attention has been directed into investigating the combined impact of vitamin C and vitamin E on aquatic organisms. Liu et al. (2019) reported that the inclusion of dietary vitamin C (40 mg kg^{-1}) and vitamin E (40 mg kg^{-1}) in the diet of juvenile Discus Fish (*Symphysodon haraldi*) may yield advantageous outcomes in terms of growth, antioxidant defense, and digesting. According to Rahimnejad et al. (2021), the administration of 500 mg kg^{-1} of Vitamin C and 400 mg kg^{-1} of Vitamin E effectively mitigated the detrimental impacts of oxidized fish oil on the non-specific immune response and antioxidant capacity of Rainbow Trout. In a study conducted by Song et al. (2019), it was found that the combined administration of Vitamin C (300 mg kg^{-1}) and Vitamin E (400 mg kg^{-1}) effectively mitigated hepatopancreatic injury caused by oxidized fish oil. This combination treatment was observed to maintain a consistent fatty acid profile in the hepatopancreas of juvenile Chinese Mitten Crab. Furthermore, a study conducted by Ruiz et al. (2019) revealed that a meal supplemented with vitamin C and vitamin E at concentrations of 800 and 2000 mg kg^{-1} , respectively, exhibited the ability to decrease lipid peroxidation and effectively prevent the formation of granulomas in larvae of the Meagre fish species (*Argyrosomus regius*). The aforementioned findings suggest that the combined influence of Vitamin C and Vitamin E on these species mostly stems from their ability to inhibit lipid peroxidation and exhibit synergistic antioxidant properties (Table 2 - Appendix).

Other Additives with Vitamin C

In the field of aquaculture, the utilization of inosine as a feed attractant has been investigated. This practice has been found to potentially stimulate various physiological aspects in numerous species, including growth,

immunological response, tolerance to oxidative stress, and intestinal morphology (Hossain et al., 2017a, 2017b). The study conducted by Hossain et al. (2018) examined the combined impact of Vitamin C and inosine on Red Sea Bream. The experimental diets included 4 g kg⁻¹ inosine and 310 mg kg⁻¹ Vitamin C, which yielded the most favorable outcomes in terms of growth and feed utilization. Additionally, a diet containing 2 g kg⁻¹ inosine and 930 mg kg⁻¹ Vitamin C demonstrated enhancements in blood chemistry and immunological parameters. According to Li et al. (2009) and Venter et al. (2019), there have been reports indicating that a significant number of fish exhibit insufficient synthesis of proline, a compound that plays a crucial role in the cellular metabolism and physiological processes of aquatic organisms. The study conducted by Wei et al. (2020) investigated the effects of dietary supplementation of proline and vitamin C on Giant Yellow Croaker (*Larimichthys crocea*). The experimental group received a diet containing 6 g kg⁻¹ proline and 50 mg kg⁻¹ Vitamin C. The results showed that this supplementation greatly enhanced the antioxidative capacity and muscle quality of the croaker. Coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) is known to have a significant impact on the electron transport chain and the synthesis of energy (Shukla and Dubey, 2018). This compound has been found to possess a wide array of advantageous effects in various animal species (Raeisi-Zeydabad et al., 2017). Nevertheless, the impact of CoQ10 on aquatic organisms is constrained. The effectiveness of CoQ10 dietary supplementation in aquatic animals was examined solely by El Basuini's research team. Their findings indicate that the inclusion of CoQ10 or a combination of Vitamin C and CoQ10 in the diet led to significant improvements in growth performance, feed efficiency, digestive enzyme activity, biochemical blood indices, immune response, and antioxidant capacity of Nile Tilapia (El Basuini et al., 2021, 2020). Moreover, the combined impact of Vitamin C with two additional additives, namely Vitamin E and tryptophan, as well as Vitamin E and Nano-Se, has been investigated in previous studies conducted by Khan et al. (2019) and Harsij et al. (2020). The findings of these studies are presented in Table

2 (Appendix). However, further investigation is required to understand the interaction mechanism of these chemicals.

Elemental Metals and Vitamin C

According to Makwinja and Geremew (2020), Iron (Fe), Selenium (Se), and Copper (Cu) are recognized as crucial micronutrients in the field of aquatic animal nutrition. Iron (Fe) is a crucial micronutrient with a wide range of physiological roles, and a shortage in iron can negatively impact the health of animals (Jayakumar et al., 2022). It is worth noting that vitamin C has the potential to enhance the process of iron absorption by converting ferric iron into ferrous iron within the gastrointestinal tract. As demonstrated by Song et al. (2023), the inclusion of dietary iron at a concentration of 143.00 mg kg⁻¹ and Vitamin C at a concentration of 700.90 mg kg⁻¹ exhibited a significant enhancement in iron absorption and utilization in Chinese Mitten Crab. Consequently, this led to notable improvements in growth, immunity, and disease resistance of the species. Selenium (Se) plays a crucial role in the biosynthesis of selenocysteine, an amino acid that is found in the catalytic center of the GPx enzyme. This presence of selenocysteine in GPx may provide an explanation for its capacity to safeguard the host cell from oxidative damage caused by environmental factors and infectious diseases (Rathore et al., 2022). The combined influence of dietary nano-selenium and VC on growth, antioxidant capacity, immune response, and disease resistance has been observed in various species, including Nile Tilapia (Dawood et al., 2020; Rathore et al., 2022), Mahseer Fish (*Tor putitora*) (Khan et al., 2017), and Sea Cucumber (Zeng et al., 2021). Copper (Cu) is known to play a significant part in various biological processes. These processes encompass the structural integrity of liver enzymes, the formation of bone and connective tissue, the maintenance of myelin in the nervous system, and the creation of hemoglobin (Mohseni et al., 2014; El-Basuini et al., 2017). Delavari et al. (2022) conducted a study to assess the combined impact of Cu nanoparticles (2 mg kg⁻¹) and Vitamin C (250–500 mg kg⁻¹) on various aspects of Rainbow Trout. The findings revealed that this synergistic

combination led to enhancements in feed utilization, metabolic efficiency, and gut tissue structure. Additionally, the antioxidant capacity and immune system of the rainbow trout were seen to be positively influenced. The results presented above collectively suggest that the combined action of Vitamin C and metal elements is species-specific and depending on the dosage, as stated in Table 2 (Appendix).

Conclusion

On the whole, it has been well demonstrated that Vitamin C is essential for growth, development, and welfare, as well as reproduction in farmed aquatic animals. However, many areas, both applied and fundamental, still need to be explored more extensively and deeply and to fully explain the mechanisms through which Vitamin C acts in aquatic animals. For example, the mechanism of Vitamin C to regulate the intestinal microbiota and further affect the nutritional and health status of aquatic animals. Furthermore, there are differences in the requirement and metabolic level of Vitamin C for different species aquatic animal. The threshold of Vitamin C addition in the feed is also controversial. Researchers should develop a set of scoring criteria to evaluate the level of Vitamin C addition based on the different requirements of practical production. Another area of concern is the interaction between Vitamin C and other micronutrients. A scientific rationale for establishing the ratio of Vitamin C and other additives in aquatic feed deserves attention. Finally, considering the instability of Vitamin C when the feed ingredient was granulated into pellets under high temperature and pressure, microencapsulation could be an effective technology to protect Vitamin C from severe conditions during feed processing and storage parameters (Rowida et al. 2021). Vitamin C is a hydrophilic compound with six carbons in its structure, which has been investigated by many researchers due to its important health properties and great antioxidant functions. In aquaculture, Vitamin C offers many benefits, such as improving growth performance, protecting cells from oxidative damage,

enhancing immunity and reproductive. However, the effects of Vitamin C depend on the aquatic animal species and size, additive dosage, presence or absence of other micronutrients, which should be extensively studied. With the sustainable development of aquaculture, the benefits and application of Vitamin C need to be further investigated.

Abbreviation

FCE feed conversion efficiency, *PPV* protein productive value, *IgM* immunoglobulin M, *SR* survival rate, *FR* feeding rate, *FCR* feed conversion ratio, *THC* total hemocyte count, *RB* respiratory burst, *MR* muscle rate, *HSI* hepatosomatic index, *NOS* nitric oxide synthase, *ILR* intestine-body length ratio, *TP* total protein, *SFA* saturated fatty acid, *PUFA* polyunsaturated fatty acid, *cpt1* carnitine pal- mitoyltransferase1, *PPAR- α* peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor α , *HDL-C* high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, *LDL-C* low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, *TC* total cholesterol, *AST* aspartate aminotransferase, *TG* triglyceride, *VSI* visceral somatic index, *HSI* hepatic somatic index, *SSI* spleen somatic index, *KSI* kidney somatic index, *GDH* glutamate dehydrogenase, *TWG* total weight gain, *GHR* growth hormone receptors, *DAO* diamine oxidase, *ABW* average body weight, *TBARS* thiobarbituric acid reactive substances, *GnRH* gonadotropin-releasing hormone, *GLU* blood glucose, *AA* ascorbic acid, *C2PP* L-ascorbyl-2-polyphosphate, *C2MP* L-ascorbyl-2-monophosphate, *BWG* body weight gain, *DWG* daily weight gain, *IBW* initial body weight, *FBW* final body weight, *GSI* gonadosomatic index, *ACH50* alternative complement pathway activity, *Ig* immunoglobulin, *PD* protein deposition, *TSP* total serum protein, *ASA* anti-superoxide anion, *AHR* anti-hydroxyl radical, *T-SOD* total superoxide dismutase, *WG* weight gain, *LYZ* lysozyme, *SGR* specific growth rate, *CAT* catalase, *SOD* superoxide dismutase, *MDA* malondialdehyde, *IL-2* interleukin-2, *IL-3* interleukin-3, *CH50* complement Hemolytic 50%, *GPX* glutathione peroxidase, *LZM* lysozyme, *NBT* nitro blue tetrazolium, *AKP*

alkaline phosphatase, *ALT* alanine transaminase, *T-AOC* total anti-oxidative capacity, *HCT* hematocrit, *BA* bactericidal activity, *FER* feed efficiency ratio, *CF* condition factor, *PER* protein efficiency ratio, *FI* feed intake, *ACP* acid phosphatase, *HSP70* heat Shock Protein 70, *HSP90* heat Shock Protein 90, *BAFF* B-cell Activating factor of the TNF family, *TNF- α* tumor necrosis factor alpha, *IL-6* interleukin-6

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Appendix

Table 1. The effect of vitamin C on different aquatic animal species

Species	Initial weight (g)	Vitamin C form	Requirement (mg kg ⁻¹ diet)	Duration	Parameters examined	Reference
Nile Tilapia (<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>)	14.74 ± 0.016	C2MP	400	10 weeks	TWG, DWG, FCR, SGR, PER, IBW, FBW	Ibrahim et al. 2020
	8 ± 1		150	7 days	GSI	Martins et al. 2016
Common Carp (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>)	20.46 ± 0.07	C2PP	500–1000	60 days	CAT, SOD, GPX, GR, MDA, LYZ, ACH50, Ig, ALT, ALP, AST	Ghafari-farsani et al. 2022
<i>Channa punctatus</i>	5.7 ± 0.11	C2PP	38.2–47.9	84 days	LWG, FCR, PER, PD, SOD, CAT, ALP, TSP	Zehra and Khan 2021
Grass Carp (<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>)	264.37 ± 0.66	AA	57.8–156.6	2 weeks	ROS, ASA, MAD, AHR, T-SOD	Xu et al. 2016a, b, c
	264.37 ± 0.66		92.8–137.5	10 weeks	FBW, PWG, SGR, FI, ACP, IgM, ROS, MDA	Xu et al. 2016a, b, c
Koi Carp (<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> L.)	50.5–54.5	AA	200–600	60 days	WG, SGR, ABW, GSI	Betsy et al. 2021
Yellow Catfish (<i>Pelteobagrus fulvidraco</i> Richardson)	2.00 ± 0.02	AA	102.5–114.5	12 weeks	WG, SGR, SOD, CAT, GPX, MDA, LZM, CH50	Liang et al. 2017
Striped Catfish (<i>Pangasianodon hypophthalmus</i>)	3.38 ± 0.01	C2PP	350–700	60 days	NBT, SOD, LZM, CAT	Daniel et al. 2021
Japanese Eel (<i>Anguilla japonica</i>)	360 ± 10	C2MP	410.8	16 weeks	GSI, AST, ALT, SOD, TBARS	Shahkar et al. 2015
Lebranche Mullet (<i>Mugil liza</i>)	205.7 ± 11.5	AA	107–216	75 days	GSI, HSI	Castro et al. 2019
Waigieu Scaperch (<i>Psammoderus waigiensis</i>)	4.7 ± 0.45	AA	0–400	10 weeks	SGR, WG, LYZ	Le et al. 2021
Silvery Pomfret (<i>Pampus argenteus</i>)	4.8 ± 0.5	C2PP	1050	24 weeks	SGR, WG, CAT, SOD, GPX, MDA, IL-2, IL-3	Zhang et al. 2022a, b
Chu's Croaker (<i>Nibea coibor</i>)	14.17 ± 0.1	C2MP	71.46–150.26	56 days	SOD, CAT, AKP, ALT, LZM, T-AOC	Zou et al. 2020
Red Sea Bream (<i>Pagrus major</i>)	2 ± 0.01	C2MP-Mg	500–1000	2 weeks	FBW, WG, HCT, BA, LZM, SGR, FER, CF, PER	Dawood et al. 2017
Hybrid Grouper (<i>Epinephelus fuscoguttatus</i> ♀ × <i>Epinephelus lanceolatus</i> ♂)	15 ± 0.1	C2MP	148	49 days	WG, FE, PE, PPV, IgM	Cai et al. 2022
Red swamp Crayfish (<i>Procambarus clarkii</i>)	7.00 ± 0.01	AA	265.67	70 days	FBW, SR, SGR, FR, FCR, CF, THC, RB, HSI, MR, ILR, SOD, NOS	Kong et al. 2021

Golden Pompano (<i>Trachinotus ovatus</i>)	13.57 ± 0.09	C2PP	49.73	56 days	WG, SGR, SFA, PUFA, T-AOC, SOD, GPX, cpt1, PPAR-α	Zhang et al. 2019
Coho Salmon (<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>)	183.19 ± 1.91	C2MP	93.08–224.68	70 days	HDL-C, AKP, LDL-C, TC, AST, ALT, TG, SGR, MDA, T-AOC	Xu et al. 2022
Largemouth Bass (<i>Micropterus salmoides</i>)	10.87 ± 0.17	C2MP	120.46–145.35	60 days	SGR, FCR, PER, VSI, HSI, SSI, KSI, GDH, HDL-C, LDL-C, TP, SOD, GPX, CAT	Yusuf et al. 2021
Coral Trout (<i>Plectropomus leopardus</i>)	17.42 ± 0.06	AA	255.25-273.84	56 days	SGR, WGR, SR, HSI, VSI, CF	Zhu et al. 2022
Puffer fish (<i>Takifugu obscurus</i>)	10.3 ± 0.21	C2MP	2.6–779.53	8 weeks	WGR, PER, AKP, SOD, CAT, HSP70, HSP90, BAFF, TNF-α, IL-6, GHR	Cheng et al. 2018a, b
<i>Rhynchocypris lagowskii</i>	4.65 ± 0.04	C2PP	200	56 days	WG, SGR, PER, FER, FI, TP, DAO, GPX, T-SOD, T-AOC	Zhu et al. 2023
Gibel Carp (<i>Carassius auratus gibelio</i>)	77.2 ± 0.1	C2PP	225.0	88 days	GSI, GnRH, T-AOC, SOD	Shao et al. 2018

Table 2. The effect of vitamin C in combination with other additives on aquatic animals

Species	Initial weight (g)	Vitamin C form	Requirement (mg kg ⁻¹ diet)	Duration	Parameters examined	Interaction with other dietary elements	Reference
Nile Tilapia (<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>)	14.74 ± 0.016 12.4 ± 0.14 13.87 ± 0.01 14.1 ± 0.03	AA	400 400/600 100–300 500	2 weeks 56 days 90 days 8 weeks	DWG, TWG, SGR, FCR, PER, IBW, FBW, TWG, FI WG, SGR, FI, FER, SOD, CAT, LYZ, BA, WG, SGR, ALT, AST, CAT, SOD, MDA, GPX, GSH, TAC, GR NBT, SOD, GPX, CAT, MDA, FBW, WG, SGR	Chitosan-vitamin C nanocomposite (400 mg kg ⁻¹) CoQ10 (20 mg kg ⁻¹) Nano-Se (0.9 mg kg ⁻¹) Nano-Se (1 mg kg ⁻¹)	Rowida et al. 2021 El Basuini et al. 2021 Rathore et al.2022 Dawood et al.2020

<i>Labeo rohita</i> (<i>Cyprinidae</i>)	1.1 ± 0.03	C2PP-Ca	800	60 days	SGR, FCR	Tryptophan (14.2 g kg ⁻¹), Vitamin E (0.2 g kg ⁻¹)	Khan et al. 2019
Mahseer fish (<i>Tor putitora</i>)	2.30 ± 0.04	C2PP	300	60 days	WG, FCE, SGR, RBC, Hb, HCT	Nano Se (0.68 mg kg ⁻¹)	Khan et al. 2017
Rainbow Trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	11.89 ± 0.34 46.9 ± 0.32 16.86 ± 0.24	AA C2MP C2MP	200 500 600	40 days 10weeks 60 days	WG, SGR, FCR, PER, LER, AST, ALT, ALP, CAT, SOD ACH50, AST, ALP, SOD, CAT Hb, RBC, Ht, ALB	Nano Se (0.2 mg kg ⁻¹), Vitamin E (60 mg kg ⁻¹) Vitamin E (400 mg kg ⁻¹) 0.1–0.2% β-glucan	Harsij et al. 2020 Rahimnejad et al. 2021 Barros et al. 2015
Chinese Mitten Crab (<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i>)	3.53 ± 0.2 1.14 ± 0.01	C2PP	300 700.9	2 weeks 56 days	WGR, FE, DO, HPI, SOD PO, GPX, SOD, T-AOC, MDA, TP, ACP, AKP	Vitamin E (400 mg kg ⁻¹) Iron (92.25 or 143.00 mg kg ⁻¹)	Song et al. 2019 Song et al. 2023
Red Sea Bream (<i>Pagrus major</i>)	2 ± 0.01 21 8.83 ± 0.04	C2MP-Mg C2MP-Mg C2MPCa/Na	400 or 800 310–930 69	56 days 56 days 60 days	SOD, WG, FER, FI, SGR CF, VSI, HIS GPT, BUN, d-ROM, TC, HCT, WG, SGR, FI, FER, PER, PA, BA, HIS, VSI, LT50%	B-glucan (500 or 1000 mg kg ⁻¹) heat-killed <i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> (1 g kg ⁻¹) Cu-NPs (2 mg kg ⁻¹)	Dawood et al. 2017 Dawood et al. 2016 El-Basuini et al. 2017
Starry Flounder (<i>Platichthys stellatus</i>)	600–2000	AA	500	104 days	AF, RF, GSI, VSI, HIS;	Vitamin A (8000 IU kg ⁻¹) α tocopherol (250 mg kg ⁻¹)	Wang et al. 2014
Sea Cucumber (<i>Apostichopus japonicus</i>)	6.46 ± 0.03	C2PP	5000	30 days	MDA, LZM, GPX, HSP70, HSP90, H ₂ O ₂	Selenium (5 g kg ⁻¹)	Zeng et al. 2021
Discus fish (<i>Symphysodon baraldi</i>)	7.96 ± 0.61	C2MP	40	14 days	SGR, LGR, CF, FCR, SR, FBW, FBL, SGR	Vitamin E (80 mg kg ⁻¹)	Liu et al. 2019

<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	14 ± 1	AA	200	30 days	PO, GOT, GPT, SOD	Beta1,3/1,6-glucan (1 g kg ⁻¹)	Wu et al. 2016
Yellow Croaker (<i>Larimichthys crocea</i>)	137.83 ± 0.35	C2MP	50	60 days	CF, HIS, VSI, CAT, GPX, SOD, GSH, ACP, NOS, T-AOC	Proline (6 g kg ⁻¹)	Wei et al. 2020